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CRITERIA FOR PRASHASTHA (NON-POLLUTED) AND APRASHASTHA (POLLUTED) BHUMI FOR HERBAL DRUG COLLECTION

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Abstract

Herbal medicines mentioned in Ayurveda have been traditionally used in India and several other countries for centuries however in recent past population has showed more inclination towards these drugs. They have gained acceptance and more popularity leading to their manufacturing and commercialization on large scale. *En route* to accomplish this demand, a great deal of attention needs to be given to procurement of the medicinal plants. These plants need to be collected as mentioned by *Acharyas* in Ayurveda and modern guidelines set by agencies. Soil with excess of water, presence of anthills, light coloured, contaminated by industrial effluents and waste having pollutants such as heavy metals, pesticides should be completely avoided for the collection or cultivation of the medicinal plants. On the other hand herbs must be obtained from dark coloured soil which is rich in organic matter and has good texture and structure, devoid of big stones, soil having grass, soil with good microbial activity and free from contamination. Following these criteria during the collection of medicinal plants will ensure quality and effectiveness of these drugs.

Key Words:

Prashastha, Non-polluted, Aprashastha, Polluted, Bhumi, Herbal Drug, Collection.

INTRODUCTION:

Worldwide usage of herbal medicines has evidently increased in recent years especially in countries like India and China which have their traditional systems of medicine. According to World Health Organization (WHO) herbal medicine is a plant-derived material or preparation with therapeutic or other human health benefits which contains either raw or processed ingredients from one or more plants¹. In India, Ayurveda largely includes herbal formulations for the therapeutic applications. The quality of these herbal medicines can be influenced by several factors which can be broadly classified as external/extrinsic (contamination, adulteration and misidentification) and internal/intrinsic (complexity of phytochemical and non-uniformity) issues^{1,2}. This study details one of the external issues, the quality of soil, required for the herb growth and collection.

The scientific study of soil, called pedology, is an important branch which helps to analyse and understand the soil health status. Soil is essential for life on earth and is composed of both organic and inorganic matter. It acts as one of the 'universal sinks' which bears the greatest burden of environmental pollution. Pollution can be defined as an undesirable change in the physical, chemical and biological characteristics of air, water and soil which can affect the living organisms. Anthropogenic activities such as mining, transport, agriculture and indiscriminate disposal of untreated waste from industries contribute to pollutants in high and toxic concentrations. Commonly most pollutants are introduced in the environment by disposal of sewage and waste, accidental discharge or sometimes they are released as by-products from the manufacturing of something useful.

Hence the kind of soil used for the cultivation of the medicinal plants or the environment from where the wild population of the herbs is collected forms a crucial factor to ensure safety and quality of the herbal medicine.

General composition and characteristics of soil-

Texture

The relative proportion of sand (the coarsest), silt and clay (the smallest) in a particular soil determines the texture of the soil. The soil texture in turn determines the water storage in soil, aeration and how well the roots can penetrate the soil. Loam soil consisting of 40% sand, 40% silt and 20% clay is considered suitable for plant growth.

Colour

Dark coloured soils are known to absorb more light when compared to light coloured soil. This allows the soil to heat up which promotes seed germination and plant growth and encourages the process of humification.

Soil pH

The soil pH indicates the acidity or basicity of the soil. Soil which is strongly acidic lacks calcium and potassium which are essential for growth and contains high and toxic concentrations of soluble aluminium and manganese. It also lowers the level of microorganisms which are vital for soil health. On the other hand, basic soils may lack in nutrients due to their low solubility in alkaline conditions^{5,6}.

Mineral Particles

The largest component of soil is mineral particles as it constitutes approximately 45% of soil. They are basically weathered rock particles which form the basis of soil and contain minerals such as calcium,

phosphorus and potassium. These minerals help and promote the plant growth. The parent rock material defines the soil colour, texture and pH value.

Organic matter

Soil organic matter represents the organic constituents in the soil primarily composed of humic and non-humic substances. The humic substances refer to heterogeneous mixture of naturally occurring organic material arising from the decay of plant and animal residue in the environment whereas the non-humic substances include compound categories such as polysaccharides and sugars, proteins and amino acids, fats and simple organic acids. Organic matter holds clay and silt and also micronutrients together thereby contributing to the crumb structure of the soil and preventing soil erosion and leaching. It increases the moisture- holding capacity of the soil and serves as slow release of nutrients for plant and microbial growth. The colour of soil indicates the amount of organic matter with darker soils having more organic content.

Air and water

Air is essentially required for the respiration by the plant roots and for decomposition of organic matter by microorganisms. Factors such as soil pore size, continuity, temperature and Departmenth affect the aeration of the soil. Like any other life forms, water is required for plants as well, for growth and survival. It allows for nutrient mobility, it lubricates soil hence allowing root development and it is also vital for microbial mobility and action.

Further, based on the stability, the soil parameters can also be classified as illustrated below (Fig. 1).

Figure 1: Soil criteria based on their stability

***Prashastha*(non-polluted/favourable) *bhumi* according to Ayurveda and modern**

In Ayurveda, *dravyaguna* is the branch which deals with herbal drugs used for the treatment of diseases including their source, collection, preservation, preparation dosages and uses. It considers that all herbs are composed of *PanchaMahabhootas*. Plants used for dietary or medicinal purpose are closely related to the type of soil in which they are produced. Although soil is also *PanchaMahabhoota*, its composition

with respect to individual *Mahabhoota* differs at various places thereby changing its properties and action. Hence great consideration is given to collection of drug and the type of soil as this eventually determines the *guna karma* (properties) of *dravyas*³.

Acharya's have mentioned about specific *bhumi* for the collection of medicinal plants. Herbs are to be collected from soil which is unctuous, smooth/even-surfaced, tight, blackish-white or reddish soil and with grass. Jungle and *sadharan* land may be near a salt-less pond or lake is considered to be fertile^{3,4}.

According to modern research healthy, high quality soil for growing plants should have favorable tilth and sufficient Department. Good tilth facilitates water infiltration and aeration and implies favorable conditions for seed germination and root proliferation⁶. Further soil should have sufficient supply of nutrients (not limited or in excess) and good drainage system. The soil should contain minimal population of plant pathogen and insect pests whereas number of beneficial organisms including microorganisms should be large. No harmful chemicals or toxins should be present and soil should be resilient to degradation and unfavorable conditions⁷.

***Aprashastha* (polluted) *bhumi* according to Ayurveda and modern-**

According to *acharya's* of Ayurveda, *aprashasthabhumi* or infertile soil is characterized by uneven pits, big stone and deep trenches. Soil with excessive water and accumulated dirty and wastewater should be avoided. Also areas with the presence of ant hills, funeral places and desert land should be avoided for the procurement of plant drug material^{3,4}. It has been shown that the ant hill soil is rich in nutrients; however the surrounding land is generally nutrient deficient which therefore affects the plant growth and *guna karma* (properties). Also the ants are known to feed on plant parts, which is not desirable for collected plant drug.

Pollution has emerged as one of the most important environmental problems worldwide thereby raising several safety concerns. There is an urgent requirement to control soil pollution to preserve the soil fertility, increase crop yield and produce plants which are safe for consumption. Primarily anthropogenic activities can affect the soil by polluting the surface soil, underground soil or by disturbing the soil profile. Discharge of industrial effluents and solid waste, uncontrolled use of fertilizers and pesticides and pollution due to other urban activities renders the soil unsuitable for growth of any plants.

Heavy metals are among the important contaminants of the environment which have adverse effects on the health of the living organisms and potential ecological risk. Activities such as burning of fossil fuels, vehicular and industrial emissions, landfill leachates, fertilizers sewage and municipal wastes lead to heavy metal pollution. The contaminants are spread from polluted to non-polluted areas as dust or leachates through the soil. Heavy metals such as cadmium, lead, zinc, chromium and nickel when present in soil exert toxic effect on plant growth and metabolism. Further bioaccumulation of these toxic metals in plants and animals can risk human health. Collection of medicinal plants from such contaminated soil thus poses a high health risk with adverse effects.

Indiscriminate use of pesticides and herbicides has led to soil and water pollution. Use of such polluted water for plant cultivation also contaminates the non-polluted land and affects the plant growth. Seepage from landfills and also industrial effluents add plethora of contaminants to the soil therefore making them infertile.

Conclusion-

Soil is the natural medium for the growth of plants; hence it largely determines the plant constituents. Hence the type of *bhumi* or soil from which the plants intended for medicinal use are collected becomes of utmost importance. Following are the broad criteria for the soil/environment from where the medicinal

plants need to be collected as defined by Ayurveda as well as modern research.

Avoid drug collection from the soil with following criteria

- Soil having presence of big stones and trenches as well as water-logged soil
- Soil having presence of anthill/*valmika*(snake nest)
- Soil having pH of less than 5 or more than 8
- Areas where industrial waste (solid or liquid) is dumped/discharged
- Seepage from landfill or percolation of contaminated water into the soil
- Excess application of pesticides, herbicides or fertilizers
- Soil contaminated with heavy metals, petroleum hydrocarbons, solvents etc.

Collected drug from the soil having following criteria

- Land having even surface with unctuous, smooth and tight soil
- Soil which is blackish-white or reddish in colour (darker soils are rich in organic matter and are hence fertile)
- Soil with pH value of between 5 to 7
- Soil with grass grown
- Soil with good granular structure which allows for good aeration and mobility of nutrients and microbes
- Soil devoid of any chemical contamination

The above guidelines/criteria will ensure the medicinal plant material quality and effectiveness thereby preventing any adverse effects due to the source of drug collection.

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